

ISic3474

I.Sicily inscription 3474

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

funerary

monument

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2015.01.13

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Castiglione di Ragusa

Provenance**Coordinates**

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Ragusa, Museo Archeologico
Ibleo

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI336067

1. τὸ ἰ Πυτικά

2. Πυρίνοι

3. ἐποίησε

4. Σφύλος ²⁶Σκύλλος²⁶.

5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645095

EDCS 70900798

Bibliography

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